

1 **Influence of Fruit Maturity, Wounding, Inoculum Density, Inoculation Method,**
2 **and Cultivar Susceptibility on Infection of Olive Fruit by *Colletotrichum acutatum***

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9
10 **ABSTRACT**

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12 inoculum density, inoculation method, and cultivar susceptibility on infection of olive
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14
15 Inoculation of detached fruits of olive (*Olea europaea*) with isolates of
16 *Colletotrichum acutatum*, causal agent of olive anthracnose, indicated that some host
17 and pathogen factors influence infection and lesion development. Besides cultivar
18 susceptibility, fruit maturity was the most important factor affecting infection and
19 disease severity, such that fruit susceptibility significantly increased with increasing
20 fruit ripeness. Wounded fruit were more severely affected than unwounded fruit, but
21 wound effect depended on cultivar and inoculation method. Severity of fruit infection
22 increased with inoculum density, although this effect also depended on fruit maturity
23 and cultivar susceptibility. The susceptibility of selected olive cultivars to anthracnose
24 under field conditions correlated well with the response of immature fruit under
25 controlled conditions. In addition, mature fruit were highly susceptible to infection, and

1 showed fewer differences among cultivars. Based in these results, an inoculation
2 method using immature green fruit and spraying them with high inoculum densities (10^5
3 to 10^6 conidia/ml) has been proposed to evaluate olive cultivars for anthracnose
4 resistance under controlled conditions.

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6 Additional keywords: “Aceituna jabonosa”, *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*,
7 *Gloeosporium olivarum*, fruit rot.

8

9 The Spanish olive industry (oil and table) presently comprises over 2.5 million
10 ha with an annual olive oil production value exceeding \$3.6 billion in the last 4 years
11 (24). Anthracnose of olive (*Olea europaea* L.) is the most destructive disease of olive
12 fruit and it is widely distributed in many olive-growing regions of the world (11, 19). In
13 Spain, the disease is named for its characteristic fruit rot syndrome with abundant
14 production of conidia in a gelatinous matrix (“aceituna jabonosa” or “soapy fruit”)
15 under wet conditions (11, 27). Most of the affected fruit drop prematurely to the ground
16 and only a few of them remain mummified on the tree canopy (15, 19, 41). Anthracnose
17 can affect up to 100% of olive fruits on a tree, particularly in years with wet falls and
18 where susceptible cultivars are grown (40, 41, 42). Besides, a very poor olive oil quality
19 is obtained from olives harvested in anthracnose-affected areas because of alterations
20 occurring in their color (red oil), acidity, and organoleptic characteristics (11, 16). In
21 addition, severely affected trees show dieback of branches, defoliation, weakness, and
22 yield reduction (10, 19, 31, 41).

23 Two species of *Colletotrichum*, *C. acutatum* Simmonds ex Simmonds and *C.*
24 *gloeosporioides* (Penzig) Penzig & Saccardo, are the causal agents of olive anthracnose
25 (25, 26, 40). In Portugal, Talhinhos *et al.* (2005) reported that *C. acutatum* is the

1 dominant species with very limited occurrence of *C. gloeosporioides*. Even so, isolates
2 of olive anthracnose with morphological and physiological characteristics between *C.*
3 *acutatum* and *C. gloeosporioides* have been observed in southern and central Italy and
4 southern Spain (2, 35).

5 Extensive studies have been conducted to determine the effects of diverse
6 variables on infection and lesion development, yield losses, and control of diseases
7 caused by *Colletotrichum* spp. (7, 13, 20, 34). However, the influence of environmental
8 and host conditions are not well known in olive anthracnose. Mateo-Sagasta (1968)
9 showed that black fruits are more susceptible to anthracnose than green fruits. However,
10 the relationship between maturity and susceptibility of fruit has not been established in
11 olive anthracnose. Wounding is another factor that affects fruit infection by
12 *Colletotrichum* spp. (5). Although the infection of *Colletotrichum* spp. on unwounded
13 olive fruit has been reported (17, 19, 27), wounding has been found to be necessary for
14 infection of olive fruit (23), and also it has been reported that may modify the resistance
15 of some cultivars (27).

16 Olive cultivars, such as ‘Frantoio’, ‘Manzanilla de Jaén’, ‘Tempranillo’ and
17 ‘Verdial de Huévar’, have been commonly identified as resistant or susceptible to
18 anthracnose, depending on the observer and/or the site (11, 27, 29, 42). Hence, an
19 effective method to evaluate the resistance of olive cultivars under laboratory conditions
20 and a continuous assessment in the field are needed in order to clarify these
21 discrepancies.

22 The main objective of this study was to identify the optimum conditions to
23 assess olive cultivars for anthracnose resistance under controlled conditions. The
24 specific objectives were to determine the effects of fruit maturity, wounding, inoculum

1 density, and inoculation method on infection of olive fruit by *C. acutatum* under
2 controlled conditions favorable for infection and disease development.

3

4 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

5 **Olive fruit.** Olive fruit were collected from healthy field-grown trees in the
6 provinces of Córdoba and Jaén (southern of Spain). Fruit of following five widely
7 grown olive cultivars (6) with different degrees of resistance to anthracnose were used:
8 ‘Picudo’, ‘Hojiblanca’, ‘Arbequina’, ‘Picual’, and ‘Frantoio’, considered to be highly
9 susceptible, susceptible, moderately susceptible, resistant and highly resistant,
10 respectively (29). All cultivars are considered native of Spain except ‘Frantoio’, which
11 is native of Italy (6). Olive fruit were separated into six color classes from 1 (green or
12 immature fruit) to 6 (black or mature fruit) (22). Olive fruit were washed, surface
13 sterilized by immersing them in a 10% solution of commercial bleach (50 g Cl per liter)
14 in sterile water for 1 min, and allowed to air-dry on a laboratory bench. Disinfested fruit
15 were placed on plastic containers and stored at 4°C until used (less than 7 days).
16 Disinfested fruits were preconditioned at room temperature (23±2°C) for 4 to 6 h prior
17 to inoculation with *C. acutatum*.

18 **Isolates.** Two isolates (Col-10 and Col-87) of the pathogen were used in the
19 different experiments. The isolates were obtained from fruits on diseased olive trees
20 from Córdoba and Málaga provinces, respectively, in southern Spain. Both isolates
21 exhibited morphological and physiological characteristics intermediate between *C.*
22 *gloeosporioides* and *C. acutatum*, although closer to the *C. acutatum* morphospecies
23 (35). Their internal transcribed spacer (ITS) and 5.8S region of rDNA showed
24 homology with *C. acutatum* (J. Moral *et al.*, unpublished data). Single-spore isolates
25 were cultured in Petri dishes containing potato dextrose agar (Difco laboratories)

1 acidified with lactic acid [2.5 ml of a 25% (vol/vol) per liter of medium]. Petri dishes
2 were incubated at $23\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a 12 h photoperiod of fluorescent light ($40\ \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$)
3 for one week. To ensure that the spore used were viable, germination of each batch of
4 inoculum was measured prior to inoculation. Inoculum density of *C. acutatum* was
5 measured with a hemacytometer and diluted to 10^6 , 10^5 , 10^4 , 10^3 , 10^2 , and 10 conidia
6 per ml according to the experiment.

7 **Wounding, inoculation, and incubation.** Wounded and unwounded fruit were
8 included in the different experiments. Three wounds (2 mm deep and 0.8 mm wide)
9 were made on each fruit with a sterile needle before inoculation. Fruits were inoculated
10 by two methods: by immersing in a conidial suspension for 30 min, or by spraying with
11 a conidial suspension (about 0.7 ml of inoculum was sprayed on each fruit). In all
12 experiments, control fruit were immersed or sprayed with sterile water. Inoculated and
13 control fruit were incubated in humid (100% RH) plastic containers ($22\times 16\times 10\ \text{cm}^3$)
14 placed in growth chambers at $23\pm 2\ ^{\circ}\text{C}$ under fluorescent lights (12 h photoperiod, 40
15 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$).

16 **Effect of fruit ripeness.** To test the relationship between fruit maturity (color
17 class) and fruit susceptibility, olive fruit from six color classes (from green to black) of
18 the susceptible cv. Hojiblanca were inoculated by immersing them in a conidial
19 suspension (10^6 conidia/ml) of isolate Col-10 for 30 min. Wounded and unwounded
20 olive fruit were included in this experiment. The full factorial combination (6×2) of
21 treatments was arranged in a completely randomized design with two replicates (humid
22 chambers) per treatment and 20 fruits per replicate. The humid chambers were
23 incubated at $23\pm 2\ ^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the disease incidence (fruit with unequivocal symptoms of
24 anthracnose) was assessed 7 and 14 days after fruit inoculation. The experiment was
25 performed twice, and data presented are the average of the two experiments since error

1 variances were homogeneous and combined analysis of variance (ANOVA) did not
2 show significant differences between the experiments. Linear regression analyses were
3 used to evaluate relationships between ripeness of fruit (color class) and disease
4 development 7 days after inoculation. Comparison of the regression lines of fruit with
5 and without wounds was made, taking into consideration the homogeneity of variances,
6 slopes, and elevations. Data showing the effect of color class on incidence of disease 14
7 days after inoculation were subjected to ANOVA and means were compared by Fisher's
8 Protected Least Significant Difference (LSD) at $P = 0.05$ (38). Data from all
9 experiments were analyzed using Statistix 8 (Analytical Software, Tallahassee, FL.).

10 **Effects of cultivar, wounding, and fruit maturity.** Three different factors were
11 studied in this experiment: cultivar (Hojiblanca, Picual, or Picudo), wounding (wounded
12 or unwounded), and two color classes of fruit (green or black). Fruit were inoculated by
13 immersion for 30 min in a conidial suspension (10^6 conidia per ml) of isolate Col-10
14 and incubated as described above. Disease incidence was assessed 7 and 14 days after
15 inoculation as described above. The full factorial combination ($3 \times 2 \times 2$) of treatments
16 was arranged in a completely randomized design. There were three replicates (humid
17 chambers) per treatment and 20 fruit per replicate. The experiment was performed
18 twice, and data presented are the average of the two experiments since there was no
19 significant difference ($P > 0.05$) between experiments. The Area Under the Disease
20 Progress Curve of incidence (AUDPC_i) was calculated in each replication using the
21 following formula:

$$22 \quad AUDPC_i = \sum_{i=n}^n [(I_{i+1} + I_i) / 2] (t_{i+1} - t_i)$$

23 where I is the incidence (%) at i th observation, t_i is the time (days) at the i th
24 observation, and n is the total of number of observations. ANOVA was performed on

1 the pooled AUDPC_i data from the two experiments and treatment means were compared
2 using Fisher's protected LSD at $P = 0.05$.

3 **Effects of cultivar, wounding, and inoculation method.** This experiment was
4 conducted to test three different factors: cultivar (Arbequina, Frantoio, Hojiblanca,
5 Picual, and Picudo), wounding (wounded or unwounded), and inoculation method
6 (immersion or spray). The experiment was performed in two separate parts using
7 immature green fruits (color class 1) for the former and mature black fruit (color class
8 6) for the latter part. Fruit were inoculated by immersion or by spraying with a conidial
9 suspension (10^6 conidia per ml) of isolate Col-87. Disease severity was assessed 7, 14,
10 and 21 days after inoculation by using a 0 to 5 rating scale where 0 = no visible
11 symptoms, 1 = visible symptoms affecting less than 25% of the fruit surface, 2 = 25-
12 50%, 3 = 50-75%, 4 = 75-100%, and 5 = fruit completely rotted with abundant conidia
13 in a gelatinous matrix (soapy fruit), or fruit with abundant white-grey mycelium on the
14 surface. This severity scale was based on the different fruit symptoms observed in the
15 previous experiments. There were three replicates (humid chambers) per treatment and
16 20 fruit per replicate. The full factorial combination ($5 \times 2 \times 2$) of treatments was
17 arranged in a completely randomized design. A disease index (DI) and the Area Under
18 the Disease Progress Curve of severity (AUDPC_s) were calculated in each replication.
19 The DI was calculated using the following formula:

$$20 \quad DI = \left(\sum n_i \times i \right) / N$$

21 where i represents severity (0 to 5), n_i is the number of fruit with the severity of i , and
22 N is the total number of number of fruit. The AUDPC_s was calculated using the
23 following formula:

$$24 \quad AUDPC_s = \sum_{i=n}^n [(DI_{i+1} + DI_i) / 2] (t_{i+1} - t_i)$$

1 where DI is the disease index at *ith* observation, t_i is the time (days) at the *ith*
2 observation, and *n* is the total number of observations. The AUPDCs was transformed
3 to $\sqrt{AUPDC_s}$ when it was necessary for homogeneity of variance. ANOVA was
4 performed on the AUDPC_s data and treatment means were compared using Fisher's
5 protected LSD at $P = 0.05$.

6 **Effect of inoculum density.** This experiment was conducted to test the
7 relationship between inoculum density and disease severity on fruit. Green fruit (color
8 class 1) of cvs. Hojiblanca and Picual were inoculated by spraying to run off with six
9 different densities (10 , 10^2 , 10^3 , 10^4 , 10^5 , or 10^6 conidia per ml) of conidial suspensions
10 of isolate Col-87. Fruit were incubated as described above. The ID and AUDPC_s were
11 calculated 7, 14, 21, and 28 days after inoculation in each replication. There were three
12 replicates (humid chambers) per treatment and 20 fruits per replicate. The experiment
13 was performed twice, and data presented are the average of the two experiments since
14 there was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) between experiments. The same
15 experiment was repeated, but in this case only 'Hojiblanca' black fruit (color class 6)
16 were used. Treatments were compared using the orthogonal contrasts for each inoculum
17 density because the ANOVA of AUDPC_s showed a significant interaction between
18 cultivar and inoculum density. The AUDPC_s was further regressed against the logarithm
19 of inoculum density.

20 **Cultivar susceptibility under field conditions.** Disease response of the olive
21 cultivars used in the artificial inoculation experiments was also assessed in a field trial
22 of different olive cultivars at "La Mina" (37.28° N, 4.26° W; province of Córdoba,
23 southern Spain). In this orchard, 12 olive cultivars were arranged in a randomized
24 complete block design with 12 blocks and one tree per block. All trees were planted in
25 1989 and they were grown according to routine farmer's practices, including the

1 application of copper fungicides in April, October, and November of 2005 to control
2 diseases caused by *Colletotrichum* spp., *Pseudocercospora cladosporioides*, and
3 *Spilocaea oleagina* (37).

4 Four trees of cvs. Arbequina, Frantoio, Hojiblanca, Picual, and Picudo exhibiting
5 a similar level of infection were selected to determine the incidence of affected fruit by
6 *Colletotrichum* spp. after a severe anthracnose epidemic in this orchard. Olive trees
7 were harvested at different times when fruit were at the same maturity (color class 5 or
8 6) stage due to inherent differences of ripening among cultivars (6). The incidence (%)
9 of fruit with unequivocal symptoms of anthracnose was determined in a sample of 2000
10 fruit per tree. Percentage values of disease incidence (Y) were transformed into logit (Y)
11 by the expression $Logit(Y) = Ln(\frac{Y}{100 - Y})$ to make homogeneous variances (J. Moral &
12 A. Trapero, *unpublished data*). ANOVA was performed on the transformed data and
13 cultivar means were compared using Fisher's protected LSD at $P = 0.05$. Disease
14 incidence (%) of affected fruits of each olive cultivar in the orchard trial was compared
15 with the response of the same cultivars in artificial inoculations by the Pearson's
16 correlation test.

17

18 **RESULTS**

19 **Effect of fruit ripeness.** Fruit of olive cv. Hojiblanca were infected by *C.*
20 *acutatum* and showed anthracnose symptoms at all maturity stages (color classes 1 to
21 6). None of non-inoculated control fruits showed any disease symptoms. The first
22 anthracnose symptoms were observed on inoculated wounded and unwounded black
23 fruit, 4 days after inoculation. In green fruit, however, the first lesions were observed
24 associated with the wound sites 7 days after inoculation. The incidence of infected fruit
25 increased linearly with fruit maturity (either wounded or unwounded fruit), 7 days after

1 inoculation (Fig. 1). The comparison between the linear regression lines of the fruits
2 with and without wounds showed equality of variances ($P = 0.0831$), no significant
3 differences between slopes ($P = 0.6756$), and significant differences between elevations
4 ($P < 0.001$; Fig. 1). The ANOVA showed that the effects of wound and color class were
5 significant ($P < 0.001$) but their interaction was not significant ($P > 0.05$), 7 days after
6 inoculation and incubation. On the contrary, the ANOVA of the data 14 days after
7 inoculation showed that the wound, and color class effects and their interaction were not
8 significant ($P > 0.05$; Fig. 1). At the end of the experiment, all infected fruit showed the
9 characteristic general rot with abundant production of conidia in a gelatinous matrix
10 (“soapy rot”).

11 **Effects of cultivar, wounding, and fruit maturity.** Olive fruit of cultivars
12 Hojiblanca, Picual, and Picudo were susceptible to *C. acutatum*. The initial anthracnose
13 symptoms were observed on black fruit with or without wounds of cvs. Hojiblanca and
14 Picudo, 4 days after inoculation. None of non-inoculated control fruit exhibited any
15 symptom. ANOVA of AUDPC_i showed that only the effect of fruit ripening, and
16 cultivar were highly significant ($P < 0.001$); while the effects of wound and the all
17 interactions were not significant ($P > 0.05$). In inoculated green fruit, the order of
18 cultivar susceptibility was ‘Picudo’ \geq ‘Hojiblanca’ $>$ ‘Picual’. When mature black fruit
19 were inoculated, cvs. Picudo and Hojiblanca did not differ in susceptibility; while fruit
20 of cv. Picual were less susceptible than the other two cultivars (Fig. 2).

21 **Effects of cultivar, wounding, and inoculation method.** In the first part of the
22 experiment, green fruit of cvs. Arbequina, Frantoio, Hojiblanca, Picual, and Picudo
23 were susceptible to *C. acutatum* and exhibited typical anthracnose symptoms. None of
24 non-inoculated control fruit showed any disease symptom. The pathogen sometimes
25 produced abundant white-grey mycelium on the fruit surface. ANOVA of AUPDC_s

1 indicated that cultivar, inoculation method, and wound had highly significant ($P <$
2 0.001) effects on disease severity. Interactions between of cultivar \times inoculation method
3 and cultivar \times wound were also significant ($P < 0.05$; Table 1). When immersed in a
4 conidia suspension, wounded fruit in all cultivars resulted in significantly ($P = 0.0152$)
5 more AUPDC_s than those of unwounded fruit. The wounding was not a significant
6 influence ($P = 0.5246$) when green fruit were inoculated by spraying with the conidia
7 suspension. Fruit of cvs. Arbequina and Picual inoculated by immersion, with or
8 without wounds, showed higher disease severity than those inoculated by spraying. The
9 inoculation method did not have significant effect in the other cultivars. The cvs. Picudo
10 and Frantoio were significantly the most susceptible and most resistant to anthracnose,
11 respectively. In general, the resistance level of the other cultivars was ‘Picual’ \geq
12 ‘Arbequina’ $>$ ‘Hojiblanca’ but it depended on the interactions with other factors (Table
13 1). Fruit of cv. Frantoio that showed anthracnose symptoms 28 days after inoculation
14 (65%), were also evaluated 50 days after inoculation. At that time, the pathogen caused
15 a general rot (“soapy rot”) of these fruits.

16 In the second part of this experiment, black fruit of cvs. Arbequina, Frantoio,
17 Hojiblanca, Picual, and Picudo were susceptible to infection by *C. acutatum*. None of
18 non-inoculated control fruit exhibited any anthracnose symptoms. Seventeen control
19 fruits of cv. Frantoio and 12 control fruit of cv. Arbequina showed infection by an
20 *Alternaria* sp. Symptoms resulting from natural infections of the *Alternaria* sp. were
21 easily recognized by its green-grey and fluffy mycelium. Fruit infected by the
22 *Alternaria* sp. were removed from the experiment. The pathogen *C. acutatum* produced
23 typical anthracnose lesions during the first week of evaluation in the inoculated fruits of
24 all cultivars, but in the second and third weeks, the presence of white-grey mycelium of
25 *C. acutatum* that covered the fruit was a common sign of the disease. ANOVA of

1 AUPDC_s of black fruit showed that cultivar, inoculation method, and wound had a
2 highly significant effect ($P < 0.001$). Interactions of cultivar \times inoculation method,
3 cultivar \times wound, inoculation method \times wound, and cultivar \times inoculation method \times
4 wound were also significant. Cultivars Frantoio and Picudo were significantly the most
5 resistant and most susceptible cultivars respectively, in these experiments, although cv.
6 Picudo did not differ significantly from cv. Hojiblanca when wounded fruit were spray
7 inoculated (Table 1). There was no significant ($P = 0.2381$) effect of inoculation
8 method when unwounded fruit were inoculated. However, inoculation by immersion
9 resulted in significantly ($P < 0.001$) higher disease severity than inoculation by spraying
10 in all cultivars, except on cv. Hojiblanca when wounded fruit were used. Wounded fruit
11 had significantly greater AUPDCs than the unwounded fruit for both inoculation
12 methods, except on cv. Picudo that did not exhibit any significant difference between
13 unwounded and wounded fruit.

14 **Effect of inoculum density.** *Colletotrichum acutatum* caused typical lesion to
15 developed on fruit at all inoculum densities tested. None of the non-inoculated control
16 fruit showed any disease symptoms. The AUPDC_s of infected fruit increased with the
17 density of inoculum from 10 to 10⁶ conidia per ml. The ANOVA of AUDPC_s showed
18 that the inoculum density and the interaction between cultivar \times inoculum density had
19 significant ($P < 0.05$) effects. The effect of cultivar was not significant ($P > 0.05$).
20 Green fruit of cv. Hojiblanca were significantly ($P < 0.05$) more susceptible than green
21 fruit of cv. Picual when inoculated with 10⁴, 10⁵, or 10⁶ conidia per ml (Fig. 3A). When
22 black fruit of cv. Hojiblanca were inoculated, the AUDPC_s increased linearly with the
23 logarithm of inoculum density ($r^2 = 0.837$; $P < 0.001$; Fig. 3B).

24 **Cultivar susceptibility under field conditions.** The cvs. Arbequina, Frantoio,
25 Hojiblanca, Picual, and Picudo showed fruit infected by anthracnose under field

1 conditions, although two trees of the cv. Frantoio did not show any symptoms. ANOVA
2 of transformed data showed that there was a significant difference ($P < 0.001$) amongst
3 cultivars, and comparison of the means revealed that all cultivars differed significantly
4 ($P > 0.05$) in their susceptibility to olive anthracnose (Table 2). Correlation analysis
5 between disease incidence Y(%) in the orchard trial and AUPDC_s in artificial
6 inoculations indicated a significant ($P < 0.05$) correlation when green fruit were
7 inoculated. The best correlation ($P = 0.0007$) of data from inoculations closest to field
8 data occurred when unwounded green fruit were inoculated by spraying (Table 3).

9

10 **DISCUSSION**

11 Almeida reported Olive anthracnose for the first time in 1899 (4). Although
12 much research has been done on the etiology of this disease during the last several years
13 (3, 25, 26, 40), little information exists on the effects of different factors affecting
14 infection of olive fruit by *Colletotrichum acutatum* causing anthracnose of olive (19,
15 27).

16 In this study, olive fruit of several olive cultivars growing in Spain were found to
17 be susceptible to infection by *C. acutatum*. The infected fruit showed typical
18 anthracnose symptoms, although they did not become mummified, probably because of
19 the high humidity in the inoculation chambers. Abundant production of mycelium was
20 frequently observed on inoculated black fruit although this symptom has not been
21 observed under field conditions (10, 11, 41). Mycelial growth has been observed on
22 artificially inoculated fruit by other researchers (40). This phenomenon may be due to
23 high humidity during the incubation period. None of the non-inoculated control fruit
24 showed symptoms of anthracnose, but latent infections by an *Alternaria* sp. were
25 detected in fruits of cvs. Arbequina and Frantoio. Infection of olive fruits by the

1 *Alternaria* sp. seems to be associated with the location of the orchard because fruit of
2 two cultivars showing *Alternaria* sp. infections were collected from the same orchard
3 (“La Venta del Llano”, Jaén Province), while fruit of the other cultivars were collected
4 from another grove (“Jarata”, Córdoba Province). Infection of olive fruit by the
5 *Alternaria* sp. has been previously described, but its importance appears to be limited
6 (9, 30).

7 Fruit ripening, wounding, inoculum density, inoculation method, cultivar, and
8 their interactions influenced the severity of infection of olive fruit by *C. acutatum*.
9 Cultivar and fruit ripening (color class) were the most influencing factors. In general,
10 the effect of different factors on infection of fruit was not observed when the highly
11 susceptible cv. Picudo was used. Susceptibility to *C. acutatum* increased linearly with
12 fruit ripeness (Fig. 1). The increase of fruit susceptibility to *Colletotrichum* spp. due to
13 fruit maturation is a common phenomenon, which may be related to the loss of one or
14 several host resistance mechanisms that are present in young immature fruit (21, 36).
15 Although these resistance mechanisms have not been studied in the olive anthracnose, it
16 has been suggested that higher concentration of phenolic compounds in immature olive
17 fruits comparing with mature ones may account for their resistance to several olive pests
18 and diseases (38).

19 Higher susceptibility of ripe olive fruits compared to unripe ones has already
20 been described (16, 27). Under field conditions, trees severely infected by anthracnose
21 had lower yield and fruit ripen more quickly the next season (fall) than fruit of healthy
22 trees. In trees that show infection by anthracnose one year and look weak, anthracnose
23 epidemics usually start earlier in the next season than in trees with higher yields (J.
24 Moral & A. Trapero, *unpublished data*). On the other hand, our results showed that
25 immature fruit are better than mature ones to assess for susceptibility or resistance of

1 olive cultivars to anthracnose. Immature and unwounded olives fruit have been
2 successfully used to assess differences in virulence among isolates of *Colletotrichum*
3 spp. (1, 32, 33, 35).

4 Wound is another factor affecting infection by *Colletotrichum* spp., although the
5 most common means of penetration of *Colletotrichum* spp. is by direct penetration of
6 plant cuticles (5, 19). In our experiments, wound was not necessary to produce infection
7 but did facilitate it as occur in other hosts (14). Infection by *C. acutatum* in unwounded
8 olive fruit has been previously reported (17, 27, 35, 40), but in general infection
9 progresses more quickly if olive fruit are wounded (18, 19). Mateo-Sagasta (1968)
10 suggested that resistance of some cultivars under field conditions could change with the
11 presence of wounds on the fruits caused by the olive fly (*B. oleae*). In our study, the
12 effect of wounds on infection of the olive fruit was influenced by the inoculation
13 method. In general, the effect of wound was greater when fruits were inoculated by
14 immersion in the conidial suspension. Inoculation of fruit by the immersion method
15 probably favored the introduction of inoculum through wounds in the fruit. Although
16 susceptibility of cultivars in inoculated fruit varied with different factors and their
17 interactions, greater and clearer differences amongst cultivars were observed when
18 immature fruit were inoculated by spraying. This inoculation method is also closer to
19 the natural inoculation process.

20 Anthracnose severity in inoculated olive fruits increased as the density of
21 inoculum increased (Fig. 3). This result is consistent with previous inoculations of
22 *Colletotrichum* spp. in other host plants (13, 34). In our study, anthracnose symptoms
23 also developed on olive fruit inoculated with a very low inoculum density (~10 conidia
24 per fruit). These results differed from previous studies (27, 34). Our results suggest that
25 still when there is a low concentration of inoculum in an olive orchard yield losses can

1 occur due fruit infection. However, differences in resistance between the cvs.
2 Hojiblanca and Picudo were easier observed when higher inoculum densities (10^4 , 10^5
3 and 10^6 conidia per ml) were used (Fig. 3).

4 In this study, the cv. Frantoio was the most resistant to anthracnose, whereas cv.
5 Picudo was the most susceptible, while the rest of the cultivars showed an intermediate
6 susceptibility to infection. In general, the order of resistance of these cultivars to
7 anthracnose was ‘Picual’ \geq ‘Arbequina’ $>$ ‘Hojiblanca’, but the resistance depended on
8 the various factors and their interactions that were investigated in these experiments. In
9 the field, highly significant differences in resistance to anthracnose were found among
10 cultivars, and the resistance levels were ‘Frantoio’ $>$ ‘Picual’ $>$ ‘Arbequina’ $>$
11 ‘Hojiblanca’ $>$ ‘Picudo’. This result is consistent with previous observations (29, 42). In
12 contrast, the cv. Frantoio has been identified as susceptible to anthracnose in Argentina
13 (11). Furthermore, we observed that a portion of fruits affected by anthracnose was
14 blighted on the branches because of defoliation and dieback of the branches (another
15 syndrome of the disease) (31, 41). This last syndrome due to anthracnose under field
16 conditions was only recently observed (J. Moral and A. Trapero, *unpublished data*).

17 The susceptibility of olive cultivars to *C. acutatum* infection under artificial
18 inoculation in the laboratory has shown a strong correlation with their susceptibility
19 under field conditions, particularly when immature and unwounded fruit were
20 inoculated by spraying ($r = 0.993$; $P = 0.0007$). In addition, anthracnose incidence
21 measured as the percentage of affected fruit in each tree seems to be a good method to
22 assess olive anthracnose under field conditions. This evaluation is best done when olive
23 fruit reach maturity (color class 5 to 6). We have observed that, when fruit are past
24 maturity, all cultivars may show complete rot (“soapy rot”), independent of their
25 susceptibility to anthracnose.

1 Our results demonstrate the importance of using less susceptible and/or late
2 maturing cultivars, and early harvest as strategies to control olive anthracnose. In
3 regions favoring olive anthracnose, recommended control practices include early
4 harvesting of olives fruit (41), and using cultivars that ripe more slowly (8). These
5 control methods are very important because *C. acutatum* has been shown to have a low
6 sensitivity to copper fungicides (37), and the use of organic fungicides in olive orchards
7 is limited during the fall and winter in Spain (12). Finally, inoculation of unripe and
8 unwounded olive fruit by spraying them with high densities of inoculum (10^4 to 10^6
9 conidia per ml) has been shown to be a good method to evaluate olive cultivars for
10 resistance or susceptibility to anthracnose caused by *C. acutatum*.

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Table 1. Effects of cultivar, inoculation method, fruit maturity, and wounding on the area under disease progress curve of severity (AUDPC_s) in olive fruits inoculated with *Colletotrichum acutatum*

Cultivar	Inoculation method ^x	AUDPC _s			
		Green fruits		Black fruits	
		No wounded ^y	Wounded	No wounded	Wounded
Spray					
Picudo		69.4a ^z	86.9a	71.2a	74.7a
Hojiblanca		44.1b	45.9b	62.4b	69.0ab
Arbequina		14.8c	27.5c	58.3bc	60.7b
Picual		14.1c	13.2d	51.3c	65.2b
Frantoio		2.4d	3.1e	28.0d	21.1c
Immersion					
Picudo		78.2a	82.2a	80.0a	86.4a
Hojiblanca		38.4b	44.2b	61.6b	75.6b
Arbequina		31.4b	42.8bc	43.3c	75.9b
Picual		30.0b	28.4c	64.6b	77.9b
Frantoio		3.3c	9.7d	33.0c	49.0c
Interactions					
	Cv×Inoc meth		0.001		0.0090
	Cv×Wound		0.0289		0.0011
	Inoc meth×Wound		NS		0.0000
	Cv×Inoc		NS		0.0289
	meth×Wound				

1 ^xTwo inoculation methods were tested: spray with or immersion in a spore suspension
2 (10^6 conidia/ml).

3 ^yThree wounds (2 mm deep and 0.8 mm wide) were made in each fruit with a sterilized
4 needle before inoculation.

5 ^zIn each column, mean values followed by the same letter are not significantly different
6 according to Fisher's protected LSD at $P = 0.05$.

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Table 2. Incidence of anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum* in five olive cultivars under field conditions^x

Cultivar ^y	Affected fruits ^z (%)
Frantoio	0.05 a
Picual	4.4 b
Arbequina	10.7 c
Hojiblanca	54.5 d
Picudo	85.7 e

^xFour trees of each olive cultivar showing a similar infection level were selected in an orchard trial affected by a severe epidemic of anthracnose in 2005.

^yFive olive cultivars differing in anthracnose susceptibility were selected from previous studies (Moral *et al.*, 2005).

^zPercentage of affected fruit was calculated in a sample of 2000 fruit per tree. All mean values are significantly different according to Fisher's protected LSD Test at $P = 0.05$.

Percentage data (Y) were transformed by the logit function, $Logit(Y) = Ln\left(\frac{Y}{100 - Y}\right)$, for homogeneity of variance.

1 Table 3. Correlation between anthracnose incidence in five olive cultivars in an orchard
 2 trial and disease severity in olive fruit of the same cultivars inoculated with
 3 *Colletotrichum acutatum*

Inoculation treatment ^y	Pearson's test parameter ^z	
	r	P-Value
Green fruits + Spraying + Unwounded	0.993	0.0007
Green fruits + Spraying + Wounded	0.972	0.0055
Green fruits + Immersion + Unwounded	0.897	0.0391
Green fruits + Immersion + Wounded	0.899	0.0381
Black fruits + Spraying + Unwounded	0.786	0.1151
Black fruits + Spraying + Wounded	0.646	0.2394
Black fruits + Immersion + Unwounded	0.787	0.1140
Black fruits + Immersion + Wounded	0.638	0.2463

5
 6 ^yInoculations were made using two fruit maturity classes (Green or Black), two
 7 inoculation methods (Spraying or Immersion), and two fruit wounding treatments
 8 (Wounded or Unwounded).

9 ^zCorrelation coefficient (r) and probability value (P-value) using the Pearson's
 10 correlation test.

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LEGEND TO THE FIGURES

Fig. 1. Effect of fruit maturity on anthracnose incidence in ‘Hojiblanca’ olive fruit inoculated with isolate Col-10 of *Colletotrichum acutatum*. **A** and **B**, 7 and 14 days after inoculation, respectively. Fruit maturity was assessed with a 1 to 6 color class scale (1 = immature green fruit, 6 = mature black fruit). For each color class, mean values with the same letter are not significantly different according to Fisher’s protected LSD test at $P = 0.05$.

Fig. 2. Effect of fruit maturity and cultivar susceptibility on the area under the disease progress curve of incidence (AUDPC_i) in olive fruit inoculated with isolate Col-10 of *Colletotrichum acutatum*. Two maturity classes (green and black fruit) and three olive cultivars (Hojiblanca, Picual, and Picudo) were used. Bars represent the average of 80 each wounded and unwounded fruit. For each maturity class, mean values topped with the same letter are not significantly different according to Fisher’s protected LSD test at $P = 0.05$.

Fig. 3. Effect of inoculum density on the area under the disease progress curve of severity (AUDPC_s) in olive fruits inoculated with the isolate Col-87 of *Colletotrichum acutatum*. **A**, green fruit of cvs. Hojiblanca and Picual. **B**, black fruit of ‘Hojiblanca’. For each inoculum density, mean values with the same letter are not significantly different according to orthogonal contrasts at $P = 0.05$.

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Fig. 1

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Fig. 2

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Fig. 3.